

EFFECTS OF DIMENSIONAL STABILITY FOR SPACE TELESCOPE COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Jae-San Yoon¹, Geeyong Park² and Jae-Hung Han³

¹Department of Aerospace Engineering, KAIST, Daejeon 305-701, South Korea
Email: straight@kaist.ac.kr, web page: <http://sss.kaist.ac.kr>

²Department of Aerospace Engineering, KAIST, Daejeon 305-701, South Korea
Email: parkji1202@kaist.ac.kr, web page: <http://sss.kaist.ac.kr>

³Department of Aerospace Engineering, KAIST, Daejeon 305-701, South Korea
Email: jaehunghan@kaist.ac.kr, web page: <http://sss.kaist.ac.kr>

Keywords: Composite telescope structure, Thermal deformation, Out-gassing deformation, Precise Measurement, Mechanical dilatometer, Dimensional stability

ABSTRACT

The size of optical payloads installed on spacecraft is getting larger in order to obtain higher resolution in a given altitude. As those large optical structures become more vulnerable to the external disturbances such as thermal, out-gassing and vibrations, the dimensional stability becomes more important to achieve the desired optical performance. This study introduces the precise measurement method for the thermal and out-gassing deformation of the carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) used for space telescope structures. An interferometer based system was used for the thermal deformation measurement, and a long-term stable optical scale sensor system measured the out-gassing deformation of the CFRP for several days.

Data-based integrated analysis is proposed for the preliminary design phase of space telescope composite structures. The integrated simulation consists of a structural part and an optical part. The first part uses the finite element method with experimental CFRP properties, and calculates the thermal, out-gassing and vibration loading response of the composite structures. The second part represents the parametric designed optical performance and its degraded performance due to the dimensional instability caused by the environmental disturbances. We modelled the space telescope as Cassegrain type having a circular CFRP tube structure. The finite element model of the CFRP tube structure and corresponding modular transfer function (MTF) value of the optical system were generated. The thermal loading, vacuum out-gassing and vibration loading were applied to the model to analyse structural responses, and these responses were recalculated as a MTF distribution and image simulation for the qualitative analysis of image quality degradation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The structure of the optical payload needs to keep its alignment of optical components in the operation environment because performance of the payload is very sensitive to its dimensional stability. The dimensional stability becomes a bottle-neck as the size of the optical structure becomes large to obtain a better performance. The carbon fiber reinforced-plastic (CFRP) has been now widely adapted for large space optical structures due to its light weight and low thermal expansion characteristics [1]. Before the CFRP is applied to the full scale optical structure, the effect of the dimensional stability should be evaluated in the space environment. The enlarged CFRP structure is exposed to periodic temperature changes, vacuum out-gassing and transmitted vibration from satellite components; they cause dimensional instability and corresponding degradation of the optical performance.

In this paper, an evaluation method is introduced for the dimensional stability of the optical CFRP structure; experimental measurements of small deformation in the space environment and preliminary analysis related to the dimensional stability of the composite structures are shown. The thermal and

out-gassing deformations of the CFRP are measured by an interferometer and encoder-based mechanical dilatometer in a vacuum chamber, respectively; these systems were proposed in our previous study [2]. The measured data of the CFRP specimens are used for the integrated analysis of the CFRP structure, which is a huge composite tube structure of a Cassegrain type telescope. The thermal, out-gassing deformation and the response of the vibration loading on the CFRP structure are simulated using the finite element method, and the corresponding effect on the optical performance of the system is also evaluated.

2 DIMENSIONAL STABILITY EVALUATION OF CFRP SPECIMEN

2.1 Thermal deformation of CFRP specimen

A thermal deformation measurement system was developed using a thermal vacuum chamber and an optical interferometer [3]. The chamber capable of achieving less than 10^{-5} torr vacuum can change the temperature of the composite specimen from 0 to 110 °C. A rotary and a diffusion pump are used to obtain the vacuum state, and a heat shroud is used to control the temperature of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 1. Thermistors are attached to the measured CFRP specimens to monitor the temperature of the specimen while the interferometer measures the thermal deformation of the specimen. The optical components of the interferometer are located outside of the heat tunnel to avoid the thermal effects on the interferometer; further details of the thermal deformation measurement system are given in the authors' previous work [2].

The CFRP specimens are made of M55J/Cyanate prepregs; longitudinal ($[0]_{16}$) and transverse ($[90]_{16}$) specimens are made, and their anisotropic coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) values is measured. The temperature of the specimens is changed from 13 to 23 °C; this variance reflects the operational temperature range of the optical payload. The four specimens are made out of 16 prepregs; each specimen possesses a thickness of 2 mm, a width of 30 mm, and a length of 300 mm for the longitude and 100 mm for the transverse. The resulting CTE value of the longitudinal specimen is $-0.92 \pm 0.02 \cdot 10^{-6}$ /K, and the transverse specimen is $38.8 \pm 0.39 \cdot 10^{-6}$ /K; these values are calculated from the strain per temperature. The CTE of the longitudinal direction, parallel to the carbon fiber, is a very small negative value; however transverse has a relatively large positive CTE value. If the prepregs are laminated properly, the absolute CTE value of the CFRP can be minimized for all directions. Minimizing the CTE value of the CFRP plate will be discussed in the next section.

2.2 Out-gassing deformation of CFRP specimen

Compared to the thermal deformation environment where it takes about one hour for the specimens to change 10 K, the outgassing process of CFRP takes a much longer time (about several hundred hours). Therefore, the out-gassing measurement system not only needs accuracy, but also long-term stability during the measurement. In order to fulfill the requirements, an optical scale sensor, Renishaw's RGH-25F model, is used because it is capable of high resolution and a long-term operation without drift [2]. A dilatometer structure, which relays the deformation of composites to the optical scale sensor, was designed, and it satisfies two conditions: having enough flexibility to deliver the precise deformation and preventing the effect from the external disturbances.

The dilatometer, including the sensor module and reference structure, is made of Invar to prevent thermal disturbances, and the kinematic coupling on the bottom of the dilatometer isolates the dilatometer from any unexpected mechanical distortion. The out-gassing deformation of the CFRP is transmitted to the optical scale sensor by two 0.5 mm thick flexible beams and a probe part connecting the gap between the scale and the reader, as shown in Fig. 1. In order to prevent the separation of the probe from the specimen, about 100 μ m of initial displacement is applied between the reader and the scale. The groove in the reference frame helps to fix the CFRP specimen which minimizes the angular

position uncertainty of the specimen. The stability and precision of the system should be verified in the simulated space environment provided by the vacuum chamber. Details related to the system validation were described in a previous study [2], which showed that the system can be stable for more than 300 hours and has enough accuracy and minimal uncertainty in the vacuum chamber.

The outgassing deformation was measured in the vacuum condition with a constant temperature (25 ± 1 °C, $\sim 10^{-5}$ Pa) for more than 300 hours in the thermal vacuum chamber. Similar to the thermal deformation measurement, four specimens are provided: two longitudinal ($[0]_{16}$) and transverse ($[90]_{16}$) specimens with a thickness of 2mm, a width of 30mm, and a length of 210 mm. They were preserved in atmospheric condition (25 ± 1 °C, RH 59 %, and 1013 hPa) for more than three weeks before the measurement began. The relative humidity of the specimen is kept in the specimen chamber, which affects the amount of moisture of the specimen. The resulting average outgassing of the longitudinal lamina is $-2.54 \pm 0.046 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and the transverse lamina is $-77.225 \pm 0.79 \cdot 10^{-6}$. These values were calculated as the strain of the specimen.

Figure 1: Configuration of thermal and out-gassing deformation measurement of CFRP.

3 INTEGRATED ANALYSIS OF CFRP STRUCTURE

The most common optical system for spacecraft is the Cassegrain type telescope, which consists of a large primary mirror and a tube structure supporting the distance between the primary and the secondary mirror. The tube structure is one of the sensitive components for the dimensional stability, de-space and line of sight jitter, because it mainly supports the distance between these two mirrors. In

this part, we analyze the space environmental effects on the de-space and jitter of the tube structure. The effect of the dimensional instability on the tube structure is represented as the modular transfer function (MTF) and image simulation which shows the optical performance of the system as shown in Fig. 2. The dimension of the CFRP tube structure is determined by several optical requirements such as ground sample distance and altitude. We selected a representative telescope model having 0.7 m ground sample distance at 685 km altitude, and the model is similar to the KOMPSAT III optical payload [4]. The determined system has F/# as 12, an effective focal length of 8.6 m, and 8.75 μm of CCD pixels. The corresponding CFRP tube structure has 1.2 m length and 1 m diameter with 2mm thickness. The stacking sequence of the CFRP structure is $[0/45_2/0_2/-45_2/0]_s$, which is result of the optimization method of the lay-up sequence [5]. A finite element model of the tube structure consists of a composite layer model of Shell99 in ANSYS, and 1536 elements are used to form the tube shape. For the static deformation caused by thermal and out-gassing loading, 10 K of temperature variance and vacuum condition from 1013 hPa (relative humidity 59%) to 10^{-5} Pa are applied; -3.63 and -7.95 μm de-space occurred for each case.

The vibration loading of reaction wheel assembly (RWA), one of the jitter generating sources in spacecraft, is applied to the finite element model by the modal state space model. The modal shape of the tube structure is extracted, and the vibration is applied in the frequency domain. More detailed explanation about the method is described in our previous study [6]. We assume that 20 % amplitude of vibration from the RWA with 50 Hz rotating frequency is transmitted to the CFRP tube structure. The structural response of the CFRP tube structure caused by the transmitted vibration is shown in Fig. 3; a peak is observed for the harmonic number of 50Hz. The amplitude of the peaks is assumed to be vibration amplitude of the focal plane of the telescope.

We can assume that the large size optical system in spacecraft is a diffraction limited system due to its high performance. With this assumption, the performance of the system, represented as the MTF value, is obtained by analytic solution. Our previous studies [2, 6] showed the optical system performance can be represented as MTF and corresponding image simulation with few design parameters mentioned above. The MTF change due to the static deformation and vibration can be calculated, as shown in Fig. 4. Corresponding image simulation results are also shown in Fig. 5; the image quality degradation is remarkable at thermal deformation while degradation due to jitter and out-gassing is less decisive.

Figure 2: Configuration of integrated simulation.

Figure 3: Structural response of the CFRP tube structure in frequency domain.

Figure 4: MTF changes due to the dimensional instability, out-gassing, thermal and jitter loading, of the CFRP tube structure.

Figure 5: Image quality degradation due to the thermal, out-gassing and vibration loading.

4 CONCLUSION

The dimensional stability of the composite telescope and its effect on the optical performance was evaluated in the operation condition with thermal, out-gassing and vibration loading. The dimensional instability caused by the thermal and out-gassing loading was measured by the precise deformation measurement system with a simulated space environment provided by the thermal vacuum chamber. The optical interferometer for the thermal deformation and the encoder-based dilatometer for the out-gassing deformation were used, and the anisotropic characteristics of the composite specimen were shown.

Based on the experiment data, the finite element model of the CFRP tube structure, which is a crucial component for the dimensional stability of the optical telescope, was analyzed for the thermal, out-gassing, and vibration loading of the space environment. The static deformation caused by the thermal and out-gassing deformation was calculated by the finite element method; about 3.5 μ m and 7.7 μ m de-space induced by out-gassing and thermal loading, respectively. The vibration loading of the RWA was analyzed by a modal state space model when RWA rotated at about 50Hz. The effect of the de-space and jitter were represented as the MTF of the optical system; the MTF of the original optical system was determined by a few design parameters of the diffraction limited system. The de-space caused by the thermal deformation severely degraded the MTF and image quality, while the out-gassing deformation and jitter slightly changed the MTF value. The study showed that the preliminary analysis method is meaningful before the design of the composite structure is fully matured. Simple optical analysis helps the engineers receive rough guidelines for the dimensional stability of the structure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Global Surveillance Research Center (GSRC) program funded by the Defence Acquisition Program Administration (DAPA) and Agency for Defence Development (ADD).

REFERENCES

- [1] A.A. Abusafieh, D.R. Federico, S.J. Connell, E.J. Cohen, and P.B. Willis, "Dimensional stability of CFRP composites for space based reflectors", *Proceedings of SPIE*, Vol.4444, 2001, pp. 9-16.
- [2] J.S. Yoon, H.I. Kim, J.H. Han, and H.S. Yang, "Effect of Dimensional Stability of Composites on Optical Performances of Space Telescopes", *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 2014, pp. 40-47.
- [3] H.I. Kim, J.S. Yoon, H.B. Kim, and J.H. Han, "Measurement of the thermal expansion of space structures using fiber Bragg grating sensors and displacement measuring interferometers", *Measurement Science and Technology*, Vol.21, No. 8, 2010, 085704 (10pp)
- [4] http://www2.informatik.hu-berlin.de/cv/documents/Fusion_Workshop_11.2006/02_Eckardt.pdf (accessed 16th July 2011)
- [5] D. Lee, "HygroThermal Design of High Stability Telescope Structure", *Proceeding of SPIE*, Vol.6024, 2005, pp. 507-516.
- [6] D.O. Lee, J.S. Yoon, and J.H. Han, "Development of integrated simulation tool for jitter analysis", *International Journal of Aeronautical & Space Sciences*, Vol. 13, No. 1, 2012, pp. 64-73.